

TRANSPARENT MoO_x AND SiO_x WINDOW LAYERS FOR HETEROJUNCTION SILICON SOLAR CELLS

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ABSTRACT: Emitter and buffer layers more transparent than amorphous Silicon is one of the improvement needed in amorphous/crystalline silicon heterojunction technology to reach the limit efficiency of silicon based solar cell. Recent studies have demonstrated the suitability of sub-stoichiometric Molybdenum Oxide as hole extracting layer in heterojunction solar cells based on n-type crystalline Silicon. However, up to now it has mainly been used in combination with amorphous Silicon, so limiting its potential as transparent emitter. This work investigates on a hole-selective contact based on the combination of a passivating hydrogenated amorphous Silicon Oxide and Molybdenum Oxide which, with their high band gaps (respectively 1.9 and 3.5 eV), should lead to best cell performances if compared to heterojunction devices based only on amorphous Silicon. Solar cells have been produced and optimized in terms of layers thicknesses. The widely reported problem of s-shape in the light current-voltage characteristics, due to undesired barrier formation against photo-carrier collection, is addressed and solved. The temperature response of the devices is also studied, and the Molybdenum Oxide film stability under thermal treatment up to 130°C is demonstrated when addressing the appropriate thermal treatments sequence.

Keywords: heterojunction; passivation; transparent oxides.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues in the fabrication of efficient solar cells is charge separation at the electrodes, which can be accomplished in two ways. The first one is the formation of charge-selective contacts, which establish a potential gradient and lead to holes/electrons collection while simultaneously blocking the complementary carriers. The second one is the surface passivation of crystalline silicon (c-Si), in order to minimize carrier recombination during charge transmission towards the outer electrodes. In amorphous/crystalline silicon heterojunction (HJ) solar cells both these effects are attained by doped and intrinsic hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) layers. However, the use of a-Si:H films is one of the major limits to high photocurrent generation due to the a-Si:H bandgap restricted to 1.7 eV [1], which introduces parasitic absorptions. Therefore the idea of replacing a-Si:H films by wider bandgap passivating layers is becoming of relevant interest [2]. To this aim this work investigates hole-selective contacts based on the combination of passivating hydrogenated amorphous Silicon Oxide (a-SiO_x:H) and sub-stoichiometric Molybdenum Oxide (MoO_x, 2<x<3) thin films.

MoO_x and other transition metal oxides have been studied for many years due to their potential applications as emitters (or, more appropriately, hole-selective contacts [3]) for silicon based [2,4-6] solar cells. Thermal evaporation of MoO₃ powders leads to films of a slightly sub-stoichiometric material (MoO_x), in which the reduced Mo oxidation state produces an oxygen vacancy defect band slightly below the conduction band [7]. The material is characterized by high transparency and wide bandgap (3-3.8 eV), typical resistivity around 10⁶ Ω·cm and work function between 4.5 and 6.7 eV [5,8,9]. MoO_x has already been successfully integrated in silicon HJ cells achieving high efficiency [2,10,11]. Although non-passivated MoO_x has shown encouraging performances in solar cells [10], passivation of the c-Si surface still remains the key factor for the best cell performances [4].

On the other hand, a-SiO_x:H produced by RF-PECVD (Radio Frequency-Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition) can be considered appealing in mass production of HJ solar cells because it has already

demonstrated its good passivation capabilities [12-14] and has been successfully integrated in Si-based solar cells [1,13,15,16] as buffer or emitter layer. With respect to a-Si:H films, which are typically characterized by a band gap energy (E_g) of 1.7 eV [17], a-SiO_x:H has the advantage of improved thermal stability [14,18] and higher transparency due to its E_g larger than 1.8-1.9 eV [1,12,19].

The aim of this study is to test the feasibility of the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x stacked window for hole extraction in HJ cells.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Flat, n-type doped c-Si wafers with <100> orientation, 1-5 Ω resistivity and 250 μm thickness were used as substrates for the deposition of the samples. The substrates were cleaned according to standard SC1 and SC2 procedures [20], then dipped in 1% Hydrofluoric Acid (HF) for 60 seconds before the subsequent deposition steps. Thin layers of a-SiO_x:H were deposited for surface passivation on both sides of several n-type c-Si wafer by RF-PECVD in a parallel plate reactor. The deposition temperature was 250°C, while the RF power density was 18 mW/cm². The reactive gas mixture flow rates were 120 sccm of silane (SiH₄) diluted in Ar at 5%, 1.5 sccm of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and 200 sccm of hydrogen (H₂), at a total pressure of 2000 mTorr. The ratio between the CO₂ and (CO₂+SiH₄) flow rates was $f_O = \frac{[CO_2]}{[CO_2]+[SiH_4]} = 20\%$. MoO_x films with various thicknesses were grown by thermal evaporation from MoO₃ pellets at a 10⁻⁷ mbar base pressure. The film thickness was controlled by a calibrated quartz balance. A Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) layer of Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) for efficient lateral contact formation was sputtered over the MoO_x film at different substrate temperatures. The top contact was completed by a Silver grid with 1 mm-spaced 200 μm wide and 1.5 μm thick fingers.

Thermal treatments were carried out on single films and complete cell structures in a programmable ATV static furnace, in a nitrogen flux.

Reflectance (R) and Transmittance (T) measurements

were performed in a Lambda 950 Perkin Elmer UV-VIS-NIR Spectrophotometer equipped with a 15 cm integrating sphere. Lifetime measurements were carried out with a flash lamp in a WCT 120 Sinton Quasi-Steady State Photoconductance Decay measuring apparatus at a minority carrier density injection level in the order of 10^{15} cm^{-3} . The valence band region of MoO_x was investigated by Ultra-Violet Photoemission Spectroscopy (UPS) to determine the work function via excitation by the 21.2 eV radiation of the HeI line. Current-Voltage (J-V) characteristics of the cells were measured under dark and light standard conditions (1-sun, 25°C , AM 1.5G) in a calibrated Class A solar simulator. Spectral Internal Quantum Efficiency (IQE) was evaluated by measures of External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) and Reflectance.

Cross sectional TEM samples were prepared in the (110) orientation and analyzed with High Resolution TEM using a JEOL 2010f HR TEM operating at 200 keV.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 a-SiO_x:H layer

The hydrogenated amorphous silicon suboxide layer used in this work was extensively studied and characterized [19]. Average optical constants were evaluated for 12 nm thick a-SiO_x:H layers, finding for n and k at 630 nm values of 3.6 and 0.004 respectively, and $E_g=1.9$ eV, revealing the transparency of the material. The average effective lifetime of these samples was 2.6 ms, with an Implied V_{OC} of 736 mV. After thermal annealing at 300°C for 10 minutes, the optical parameters and V_{OC} remained substantially unchanged, while the lifetime increased to 3.6 ms. The oxygen inclusion in a-SiO_x:H films was evident from FTIR-ATR measurements in the $1850\text{-}2300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, not shown here, where the peaks related to the stretching of the Si-H bond are located.

A particular characteristic common to other amorphous thin films is the c-Si surface passivation achievable as a function of a-SiO_x:H thickness [21]: the passivation capabilities are best fulfilled when thicker films are deposited, reaching effective lifetimes well above the millisecond and Implied V_{OC} values exceeding 700 mV. Below 8 nm both values of lifetime and Implied V_{OC} rapidly decrease; a thickness of 5 nm constitutes the lower limit to obtain an adequate passivation of the c-Si surface with an effective lifetime of 200 μs , corresponding to 490 μm of diffusion length in n-type silicon. It is worth to remark, however, that when a 5 nm thick a-SiO_x:H layer was introduced in a complete HJ cell, the effective lifetime of the structure reached 1.7 ms after a thermal annealing at 300°C for 10 minutes.

3.2 MoO_x layer

Before implementing MoO_x films as hole-collecting layers in HJ solar cells, the electro-optical characteristics of samples grown on glass were measured.

The linear extrapolation of the UPS measurements, reported in Fig. 1, provided a work function value of 5.5 eV for the as-deposited sample, while after thermal annealing at 180°C the value dropped to 5.2 eV.

Optical R and T of films with different thicknesses are shown in Fig. 2. The optical bandgap E_g was deduced by the approximated Tauc Plot for indirect transitions (inset in Fig. 2), and it was around 3.8 eV, which ensured a very low absorption of the high-energy solar radiation.

MoO_x film resistivity measured on thick layers decreased from $5 \times 10^5 \Omega\text{-cm}$ to $10^2 \Omega\text{-cm}$ after thermal annealing. The measured values were in accordance with literature and confirmed the sub-stoichiometric structure and the semiconductive behavior of the MoO_x layers even after thermal annealing [8].

Figure 1: UPS measurements on a MoO_x film before and after annealing at 180°C

Figure 2: Transmittance of MoO_x films with different thickness. The inset shows the Tauc plot and the optical bandgap of the samples

3.3 Optimization of the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x bilayer

In the initial proof-of-concept cell, the back side contact was not optimized. To obtain the base contact, the back a-SiO_x:H passivation layer was partially removed by a mechanical scratch to allow an ohmic contact of the n-type c-Si substrate with an Indium Gallium (InGa) alloy [22].

As a starting point, a 6 nm thick front buffer a-SiO_x:H layer was adopted and different thicknesses of MoO_x were tested in the range between 6 nm and 20 nm, as suggested by literature [4,5,10,23]. An ITO film was deposited over the MoO_x layer to enhance the lateral collection of the emitter layer. The initial passivation level, associated to a 600 μs effective lifetime, was partially reduced after the MoO_x layer deposition and subsequent ITO sputtering process at 100°C [24]. The effective lifetime value of 360 μs , measured on the cell structure without metal contacts, ensured an Implied V_{OC} of 675 mV. Nevertheless it is well known that further thermal processes could recover the initial passivation level [24] or even improve it [25].

The light J-V characteristics of all devices (shown in Fig. 3) proved efficient current generation capabilities, although the cells fill factors (FF) were affected by an

unwanted s-shape clearly influenced by the thickness of the MoO_x layer, as already found in literature [4]. The presence of the s-shape is the evidence of a hole-collection issue, which limits the FF of the devices below 70% [4]. It has been suggested that possible causes for this effect can be found in an interlayer between MoO_x and TCO layers [11] or in the high reactivity of the MoO_x films to the environment that changes its oxidation state and lowers its work function. Thus the key to obtain better performances is to avoid MoO_x exposure to ambient atmosphere. To exclude any contribution coming from the MoO_x/ITO interface we produced a p-c-Si/ MoO_x/ITO structure (12 nm thick MoO_x) avoiding prolonged MoO_x ambient exposure. Then we tested the current-voltage behavior of this structure obtaining a linear J-V characteristics, that confirmed both the behavior of MoO_x layer as hole extractor and the ohmic nature of the MoO_x/ITO contact. Therefore the s-shape of Fig. 3 did not depend on the MoO_x/ITO interface.

Figure 3: Light J-V characteristics of test cells with 6 nm a-SiO_x:H buffer layer and variable MoO_x layer thickness

Figure 4: Best light J-V characteristics of test cells with a 5 nm a-SiO_x:H buffer layer and variable MoO_x layer thickness

One more reason to explain the s-shape could be the excessive thickness of the buffer a-SiO_x:H layer, as suggested by literature [26,27]. Thus we reduced the buffer thickness to 5 nm. New heterostructures were produced with 5 nm thick a-SiO_x:H buffer layers and both 6 nm and 12 nm thick MoO_x layers, respectively. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that the combination between 5 nm of a-SiO_x:H and 12 nm of MoO_x gave rise to J-V curves without any s-shape, while the cell with the 6 nm thick MoO_x layer is again characterized by an s-shape.

Despite the s-shape disappearance, the FF still resulted oddly low (66%), suggesting the presence of some other detrimental effects on the cells, besides the series resistance. To evaluate this subject, we investigated the a-SiO_x:H/ MoO_x interface, as discussed in the following sections, also with the aid of band structure simulation.

3.4 Band structure of the cell

To have a detailed view of the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H/ MoO_x/ITO junction and how it works, the complete heterostructure device was described with the help of a numerical finite difference model [28,29].

In Fig. 5a the band diagram of the entire device obtained from simulation is reported at the equilibrium condition in the dark. Looking at the front side of the cell (left side in the picture), in which the most relevant part of the heterostructure under investigation lays, the effect of the MoO_x layer on the whole interface has to be carefully considered. Even though the MoO_x layer can in principle be considered as an n-type semiconductor, its electron affinity, higher than the surrounding layers, strongly bends the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H interface. Since at the equilibrium the Fermi level must be kept constant everywhere along the band diagram, the n-type c-Si depletes and it is even inverted at the interface, thus forming the junction. For the n-type c-Si this behavior is quite similar to what happens in a typical p-a-Si:H/a-Si:H/n-c-Si heterojunction device, but in this particular case the band bending within the c-Si is induced by the n-type MoO_x layer instead of the p-type a-Si:H layer.

Figure 5: Band bending at the front and rear side of the heterojunction solar cell as deduced from numerical simulations. The value of MoO_x work function adopted in (a) is reduced by 0.5 eV in (b)

Thanks to the high electron affinity and work function of the MoO_x layer, there should be no need to be concerned about the depletion of this layer at the equilibrium that, instead, in certain conditions affects the p-type a-Si:H emitter layer of the heterojunction. The relevant concern is mainly on the MoO_x work function.

Since it is lowered after thermal annealing over 180°C, as suggested by the experimental results, the band bending induced within the c-Si would be less pronounced, thus producing a lower built in voltage and some difficulties to collect carriers over the valence band mismatch at the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H interface. This effect is illustrated in Fig. 5b, where the work function and the electron affinity of the MoO_x layer were reduced by 0.5 eV.

Experimentally the effect of work function reduction produces a fill factor drop, thus remarking the difficulties of hole collection. Also the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H interface plays a role in this equilibrium. Indeed, the defect density (D_{it}) at the interface should be much reduced, as assumed in the simulation using a $D_{it} = 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, to avoid the pinning of the Fermi level toward mid-gap position, thus affecting again the carrier collection. Indeed the a-SiO_x:H layer has been already demonstrated suitable for effective c-Si surface passivation like a-Si:H film; moreover the chemical compatibility of this sub-oxide layer with any oxide growth over it favors the stability of the MoO_x layer during its growth. Since the simulations demonstrate that the investigated heterostructure effectively works as efficient solar cell, in the following paragraphs we show how to experimentally achieve similar results.

Figure 6: Dark (inset) and light J-V characteristics of the final heterojunction solar cell before and after thermal annealing at 130 and 180°C

3.5 Solar Cell performances

The optimized front structure consisting in a 5 nm-thick a-SiO_x:H/12 nm-thick MoO_x bilayer was introduced in a complete solar cell, paying additional care to minor aspects in the fabrication process. This included attention to environmental conditions to preserve the MoO_x free surfaces from unwanted parasitic oxidation and moisture adsorption, and a tuning in the ITO deposition parameters to avoid thermal stresses to the structure without losing transparency and conductivity of the ITO layer itself. According to the findings described in Section 3.3, the cells had a 5 nm thick a-SiO_x:H passivation layer on both sides of the c-Si wafer. In agreement with literature [30], a-SiO_x:H layers could achieve a moderate surface oxidation when exposed to the air. For this reason, as a precaution, we treated the passivated wafer with a fast dipping in HF 1% solution before the subsequent depositions. The back side of the cell was completed by a 10 nm thick n-type amorphous silicon film grown, as reported in [25], to selectively extract electrons. The optimized 12 nm thick MoO_x layer was evaporated on the front side of the cell, which was kept in nitrogen atmosphere before the deposition of an 80 nm thick ITO

layer. This thickness for ITO was chosen for better front side reflectance reduction. Also the back contact was covered by an 80 nm thick ITO layer. At this stage the effective lifetime value of the cell was of 560 μs and the Implied V_{OC} had increased to 690 mV.

The cell was then completed by a homogeneous Silver contact on the rear side and a silver grid on the front side, with 1 mm-spaced, 200 μm-wide and 1.5 μm-thick fingers which were thermally evaporated through a physical mask, thus determining an effective area of 4.8 cm². Figure 6 shows the light and dark J-V curves measured on the cell. The undesired s-shape was completely removed and the superposition principle of the dark and lighted curves was respected, even if not shown. In this way the FF was boosted to a value of 77.4%. These measurements confirmed that the issue limiting the FF and efficiency (η) of the previously studied samples was located at the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x interface. The photovoltaic parameters of the best cell were: V_{OC} =675 mV, J_{sc} =31.7 mA/cm², FF=77.4% and η =16.6%.

Figure 7: High resolution TEM micrograph of the window layers of the final cell.

A high resolution TEM micrograph of the front layers of the cell is shown in Fig. 7, and reveals the actual thicknesses of the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x layers, which were slightly lower than expected (4.3/8.9 nm, respectively). This could partially justify the relatively low V_{OC} of the cell which did not reach the state-of-the-art value for heterojunction solar cells, considering that the passivation is a function of the buffer thickness and the fact that the passivation properties of the a-SiO_x:H layer could in principle be further improved after simultaneous ITO deposition and thermal treatment [25], with best effects at 300°C, as already discussed in Section 3.1. On the other hand, detrimental effects of temperature on the work function of MoO_x are well known [8,31]. For these reasons, the thermal stability of the cell was investigated with the aim of both increasing the passivation quality offered by the a-SiO_x:H layer and testing the MoO_x resistance to thermal treatments.

Figures 6 and 8 report the J-V characteristics and quantum efficiencies of the final cell after sequential thermal annealing at increasing temperatures of 130°C and 180°C in a nitrogen flux for 10'. The performances of the cell slightly improved when thermally annealed up to 130°C. In particular, the V_{OC} increased up to 680 mV

because of c-Si surface hydrogenation promoted by the thermal treatment of the a-SiO_x:H layer. Nevertheless 180°C thermal annealing temperatures negatively affected both J_{sc} and V_{OC}, which lowered to 28.5 mA/cm² and 635 mV, respectively, resulting in an efficiency of 14.1 %. We suppose that this effect was related to energy band alignment modifications due to a reduction in the work function of the MoO_x layer, although the quantum collection efficiency on the front side was greatly increased thanks to the higher ITO transparency in the short-wavelength region after thermal annealing. These values were actually lower with respect to c-Si/a-Si:H heterojunction cells [32-34] despite the transparency of the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x emitter. This was mainly due to the absence of c-Si surface texturing as demonstrated by the mirror-like surfaces of these cell leading to an effective reflectance of 19.8%. Moreover, the ITO layer absorption still limited the photon transmission towards the c-Si substrate. Nevertheless the obtained results are remarkable for a structure involving for the first time to our knowledge the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x combination as HJ window layer.

Figure 8: Reflectance (line), Internal (symbol) and External (open symbol) Quantum Efficiencies of the final heterojunction solar cell before and after annealing at 130 and 180°C

The IQE measurements on the non-annealed cell (Fig. 8) proved, as expected, the reduced absorption of all front layers and the fair passivation level provided by a-SiO_x:H. Therefore the aim of manufacturing a window layer more transparent than the present state of the art of HJ solar cell was demonstrated. The effect of annealing was to improve both front passivation and transparency, as deduced by the increase of the response in the short-wavelength range, while the signal in the near-infrared range was lowered because of the modified optical properties of ITO.

In conclusion, even though a high temperature treatment would be desirable to enhance the passivation of the c-Si surface and the transparency of the cell front side, the overall behavior of the device results strongly deteriorated after a thermal treatment above 130°C.

It can be noticed (Fig. 6) that no s-shape arose, even at the highest thermal annealing temperature. These results differ from other reported in literature [11], in which the s-shape appeared and worsened upon annealing over 130°C, and was hypothetically attributed to the thickening of an interlayer between MoO_x and TCO layers. Battaglia et al. [4] reported an initial s-shape

which “straightened out” but did not completely disappear after low temperature annealing up to 60°C, and interpreted the results as a thermionic emission barrier which the holes had to overcome. In the experiments reported in this work, the s-shape issue was definitely solved thanks to the HF treatment of the a-SiO_x:H surface before MoO_x deposition, which removed unwanted surface oxidation [30].

Even though the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x bilayer is more transparent than the amorphous counterpart and the s-shape issue was completely removed, the cells efficiencies were not as good as those reported in literature [2] for silicon-based devices containing MoO_x. Optimization of the front texturing, of the thermal processing sequence, of the metal grid thickness and of ITO transparency and conductivity will help in filling the gap.

3.6 Carrier transport at interface

Focusing on carrier transport, it is worth to notice that the carrier collection by the MoO_x hole-collecting layer has two contributions. The first one arises from the thermionic emission over the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H barrier in the valence band. When the holes reach the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x interface, they immediately recombine with electrons coming from the MoO_x layer and supplied by the ITO antireflection coating. The second contribution to hole collection arises from a multi-step tunneling mechanism [35] of electrons which takes place at the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x interface with the help of band tails and defect states within the a-SiO_x:H layer, and extends up to the c-Si/a-SiO_x:H interface. This assumption is demonstrated by the exponential trend of the low forward bias (0.3 V) dark current of the heterojunction as a function of temperature reported in Fig. 9.

The interface between ITO and MoO_x is less critical. The energy barrier evident in Fig. 5a is kept very narrow if the MoO_x layer does not deplete, and therefore it can be easily overcome by a tunneling mechanism.

Finally the rear side contact of the cell, where a-SiO_x:H works as a passivating buffer layer, as also simulated in Fig. 5, did not show any issue on the carrier collection.

Figure 9: Exponential trend of the low (0.3 V) forward-bias dark current of the heterojunction as a function of temperature, revealing a multi-step tunneling mechanism

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work MoO_x as hole selective layer was successfully used in combination with an a-SiO_x:H passivation buffer layer in an n-type silicon based solar

cell. It was successfully verified that barriers at the a-SiO_x:H/MoO_x/ITO interfaces strongly depend on care taken during the fabrication processes. Once the formation of these barriers was avoided, the optimization of layer thicknesses, process flow sequence and thermal processing led to good performances of the solar cells. A V_{OC} of 675 mV and a J_{sc} of 31.7 mA/cm² were obtained together with the complete removal of the undesired s-shape on the J-V characteristics, which boosted the fill factor to 77.4% and the efficiency to 16.6%. Although the fabricated devices have quite modest performances in terms of V_{OC} and J_{sc}, FF values above 77% are nevertheless interesting, as this is generally the weak point of devices featuring MoO_x layers.

The thermal stability of the structures was investigated, recording an improvement of performances after annealing up to 130°C. Further heating brought to a general deterioration of the cell, in particular in terms of V_{OC} and FF, because of electronic modifications in MoO_x which were not counterbalanced by improvements in ITO conductivity and a-SiO_x:H passivation.

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6 REFERENCES

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